

FNS - Cloud
Food Nutrition Security

Handbook for practice-based learning in multidisciplinary projects

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Welcome and introduction

Welcome to the best practice guide for the use of practice-based learning grants within large multidisciplinary research projects.

By their very nature research projects are not predictable and require new skills, resources, and working patterns to be developed as researchers navigate issues of developing new knowledge and applications.

This guide has been developed to allow 'just in time' learning by collaborating partners to be promoted, managed, and supported during the project. The processes discussed and the advice provided are those that emerged during Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud, Grant Agreement No. 863059).

Chapter 1 Introduces elements of practice-based learning and evidence base.

Chapter 2 Explores how we can promote experiential learning and reflection upon it.

Chapter 3 Returns to the submission and how reflection and learning can be evidenced and assessed.

Appendices 1-2 Provide templates for the application and evaluators form.

Chapter 1: Short introduction to practice-based learning

Nature of learning from practice

Adults may learn through formal teaching, such as university courses, and/or through independent study. Over the last two decades, there has been increasing realisation that professional learning can and is both formal and informal at organisational, group or individual levels. It was thought that everything a person needed to know for successful performance in an occupation could be specified in advance and provided formally. Clearly, this is not the case, as the practice of our work or profession is rarely 'rule following' but requires individuals to be creative and innovate from experience and expertise to provide appropriate response to a novel situations or issues.

This is a type of experiential learning, in the sense that it is gained mostly through what people do and experience. It focuses on individuals' work practices and on experience gained from their roles throughout their careers. Practice-based learning is effectively the study of how to make such learning as effective and robust as possible and be shared with others in an ethical manner.

A common definition of learning is a *'process that brings together cognitive, emotional, and environmental influences and experiences for acquiring, enhancing, or making changes in one's knowledge, skills, values, and world views'* (Ahrenkiel, Illeris 2000). This definition makes plain that learning is not only a change in knowledge and skills but can, and probably will, also impact values and worldview. Worldview is essentially an individual's ontology, describing how they see the world and what they consider to be reality.

Illeris (2013) went on to define the *"most fundamental condition of human learning is that all learning includes two essentially different types of process: an external interaction process between the learner and his or her social, cultural and material environment and an internal psychological process of elaboration and acquisition in which new [insights and] impulses are connected with the results of prior learning"* p35.

So, we not only have to have formal or informal learning experiences, but we must then 'inwardly digest' (BCP) what it means and how it relates to what we previously knew. Most sources agree that evidence of this type of learning is change. Change can be in reference to behaviours but can also include ways one thinks about a situation or person. Historically, learning was identified mainly as a cognitive process – acquisition of new facts and understanding – but this thinking has moved on to a more holistic view in which there is a recognition that people learn by action and experimentation with new concepts. Scholars are also considering the emotional aspects of learning (Brockbank and McGill, 2006), i.e., when considering what learning is, it is important to consider the doing, thinking, and feeling aspects collectively.

Deep learning and reflection

Deep learning has been identified as occurring when individuals take responsibility for their learning to create constructs and meaning. They can describe the meaning they have achieved and justify how they have come to this understanding. Learning theories have identified that it is through reflection that deep and significant learning occurs. A comprehensive account of reflection can be found in Boud, Keogh and Walker (1985) and it may be helpful when considering reflection in the context of practice-based learning to consider that reflective learning is, *"an intentional process, where social context and experience are*

acknowledged, in which learners are active individuals, wholly present, engaging with others and open to challenge and the outcome involves transformation as well as improvement of both the individual and their organisation” Brockbank, McGill and Beech, 2002, p.6

The word **reflection** in this handbook is not simply used as a synonym for ‘thinking’. Reflection is a thoughtful (in the sense of deliberative), consideration of experience, which leads an individual to decide:

- What that experience means to them
- How it challenges and changes them
- What it means for their future practice.

The construction and assignation of meaning to experience then gives individuals the potential to look at experiences from other points-of-view. This embodies the idea that reflection can be critical and evaluative. It is critical reflection that is needed to engage in a professional studies programme, large or small. Reflection enables individuals to learn more effectively because it develops the ability to evaluate experiences – whether it is the experience of learning or doing daily work.

Reflection helps individuals to look at an experience, understand it better, and learn from it.

Much of the professional development in higher education is influenced by Schon’s (1987) reflective practitioner paradigm. Its implementation in a variety of contexts has led to reflective practice becoming an educational orthodoxy (Clegg et al, 2002). Professional learning, achieving workplace success and gaining academic honours are about meeting and exceeding our expectations often in creative and novel ways. It will produce new learning and will often challenge conventional or traditional thinking.

Practical application

What are individuals being invited to evaluate, consider, or reflect upon? The answer is – their experience of work, what they have learnt from it, and how this learning has shaped how they see the world, approach work issues, and achieve within their work setting. Reflection has some key characteristics:

First, reflection involves practical and active engagement. In the list below verbs that describe what reflection means are highlighted. Individuals are reflecting when they actively:

- **Examine** and **investigate** learning and working practices.
- Ask **questions** about their experience with a view to **trying to understand** it.
- **Probe** assumptions and the values that underlie behaviour.
- **Formulate** judgements and **develop** conclusions about actions.

Second, the purpose of engaging in these reflective activities makes individuals more aware of their experience and behaviour. They help individuals to interrogate (e.g., Why did I do that?), evaluate, make sense, and give experience meaning. As individuals become more aware of why they act as they do and assumptions that underpin their actions, they are in a strong position to change behaviours if they want to. The ability to change helps individuals to grow and develop, i.e., to learn from experience.

Several models describe how people reflect on their experience. Here are three well-known ones that approach reflection in different ways.

Reflective practitioner model (Donald Schon)

There are two types of reflection in this model:

Reflection-in-action: This is where individuals reflect on their actions while they are doing them and make immediate changes to behaviour, e.g., ‘Something isn’t working here – how can I improve things right now?’

Reflection-on-action: This is where individuals look back over what they have done, and contemplate and review it, e.g., Why did that not go so well? What can I learn for next time?

Reflective cycle (Graham Gibbs)

There are six steps to aid reflective practice in this model:

1. **Description** First describe what happened in an event or situation.
2. **Feelings** Identify responses to the experience, e.g., What did I think and feel?
3. **Evaluation** Categorise what was good and bad about the event or situation.
4. **Analysis** Explore the ‘feelings’ and ‘evaluation’ steps to help make sense of the experience.
5. **Conclusions** Ask, what have I learned from the experience?
6. **Action plan** Finally, plan and modify your actions based on your reflections.

Experiential learning cycle (David Kolb)

Reflection is a key element in successfully learning from experience in this model:

Experience First be involved in a task in an open-minded way.

Reflection Consider, that is reflect on, the experience, e.g., ask ‘What did I notice about my experience?’

Conceptualisation This reflection helps make sense of the experience by answering the question ‘What does my experience mean?’

Experimentation Finally, check out the adequacy of meanings by putting them into practice in the real world, e.g., ask ‘What do I want to do differently next time?’

This starts a new cycle of learning as individuals immerse themselves in new experience again.

Kolb’s learning cycle (**Figure 1**) is a model of the structural relations between these four modes of relating to the world, showing structural dimensions of ‘grasping’ and ‘transformation’ and resulting knowledge forms (after Kolb, 1984, p. 42).

Kolb’s definition of learning is the, “*process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience*” Kolb, 1984, p.41

There are several critiques of Kolb's cycle (see Kayes, 2002):

- it takes very little account of different cultural experiences/conditions.
- the idea of stages or steps does not sit well with the reality of thinking.
- there is scant regard for individual learning preferences.

It has, however, been influential in moving the focus of learning away from the 'instructor' to the learner and forms a useful way of understanding why individuals are asked to reflect on their learning throughout professional studies activities.

Kolb's learning theory argues that learning is a lifelong process in which personal development and work play as much a part as formal education. Ideally, experiential learning occurs when individuals involve themselves in new experiences in an open-minded way (have "concrete experiences") and reflect on their experiences from a range of perspectives (by "reflective observation"). By integrating their observations into theories (into "abstract conceptualisations"), individuals give it meaning that can be tested in real world problem-solving situations (by "active experimentation"), which provides concrete experiences for the next cycle of learning.

Figure 1. Kolb's learning cycle

Kolb argues that effective learning requires contrasting abilities that he modelled as opposites on two dimensions of learning. Abstract conceptualisation and concrete experience are contrasting ways of "grasping" experience. Thus, reflective observation and active experimentation are contrasting ways of "transforming" experiences that individuals have grasped in either or both ways. For example, the **internal**

process of reflecting on thoughts and feelings about a particular concrete work experience (e.g., new administrative procedure implemented two weeks ago), operates on that experience and transform it through attribution of meaning (e.g., “it doesn’t seem to be working as well as it should”). The **external process of acting on** the concrete experience is also a way of transforming experience, by extending it in some way (e.g., “seeing if it works better another way instead”). As this example shows, it is often necessary to utilise both reflective and active abilities to transform or elaborate or develop experience. In other words, for learning to occur, experience must be grasped and transformed, as described above.

This involves interaction between the four learning modes of:

- concrete experience
- reflective observation
- abstract conceptualisation
- active experimentation

Single- and double-loop learning and transformational learning.

When people learn, they do so at several levels. It may be learning to deliver improvement of work – ‘doing things right’ – or they may go further and consider their work in more strategic terms and find themselves questioning established norms and assumptions – ‘doing the right things’. This is identified as transformational learning (Flood, Romm 1996:10).

A good example of single-loop learning is identified in the Kolb cycle (1984), which represents an effective cycle of improvement or maintenance learning. His work on processes through which experiential learning occurs and on individual differences in styles of learning has been much used, particularly in management education, often through popularisations such as the learning styles questionnaire of Honey and Mumford (1992). However, transformational learning creates new knowledge by reconsidering assumptions or ‘norms’ inherent in single loop learning. Characteristically, old paradigms or ways of thinking are changed and redesigned in transformational learning, or double loop learning.

Chapter 2: Promoting experiential learning and our reflection upon it

Expanding our knowledge.

It follows from previous discussion that one of the most effective ways to expand learning and knowledge is to expand experience. Working practices are evolving in the natural and social sciences in response to expansion in funding of multidisciplinary and complex projects requiring scientists to work internationally and collaboratively across disciplines, cultures, language, and organisational contexts.

“Considering the enormous complexity and multifactorial causation of the most vexing social, environmental, and public health problems efforts to foster great collaboration among scientists trained in different fields are not only a useful but also an essential strategy for ameliorating these problem” (Stokols, Hall et al. 2008)

It is, therefore, appropriate to facilitate collaboration but in a way where learning can be acknowledged and reflected upon for maximum benefit to the individual, their practice, and the project.

Format for a competitive grant scheme in practice based learning

The specific requirements needed to facilitate practice-based learning were identified as:

1. **Ability to travel and work with collaborators and experience the application of new skills or knowledge in situ.** FNS-Cloud identified a competitive scheme was appropriate to facilitate the broadest and most transparent allocation of funds.
2. **Clear identification of what the learning need is for the individual and the project - what is needed and how it can be acquired.** Learning must be planned if it is to be effective and, therefore, self-reflection by the individual on their personal development is required as well as identification of how their new learning will be applied within practice in their home institution.
3. **Reflection post -learning experience to allow explicit generation of deep learning.** Individuals must provide a reflective account of how the learning experience has developed their professional practice and contributed to their work within the project.

The process designed for the scheme considered requirements as follows:

FNS-Cloud work-based learning competitive grant scheme (WBLCG)

- a. **Applicant sends a signed soft copy directly to scheme manager by email as well as posting it on a secure area of myFNSCloud.** It is important to use both approaches to ensure, as far as it is possible, that no application is missed: it would be unusual that both email and posting failed. Obtaining a signed copy is important as a means of demonstrating supervisors/ line managers/ host organisations are informed about activities of staff and students and grant permission without additional administrative burden.
- b. **Scheme manager checks copy for names, gender, contact email address, organisation and supervisor/ line manager, justification – maximum of 1000 words – costs and eligibility (i.e., FNS-Cloud beneficiary)**

This check is intended only to establish the application includes all relevant information. Typical errors included insufficient words and poor justification. Inappropriate costs were excluded without reference to the applicant and these changes explained in the award email. Justifications with too few words were returned to the applicant for amendment and must be resubmitted before the deadline for applications or within 24 hours after the close of the call. Any supporting documentation was requested at this time (e.g., confirmation of additional funding from another source).

- c. **Scheme manager distributes applications to panel consisting of at least two WP leaders and others (as required based on type and scope of application) to score completeness of information, reasons for attending, adding value to the project and contribution to deliverables on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5 = excellent).**

In collating the scores, the scheme manager must consider the status of the individual (i.e., Master or PhD student, early-career post-doctoral researcher, post-doctoral researcher/ lecturer or

senior staff) since this affects all aspects of the application. Senior staff are familiar with application processes and what is needed for a successful outcome, and more likely to add-value and understand the strategic benefits of their participation for both the network and their organisation whilst PhD and Masters students are more commonly engaged in specific activities but less aware of what is required generally or how to express their needs appropriately. Outliers (i.e., scores different significantly between the panel) were reviewed and adjusted by the scheme manager, as necessary. Once the applications had been collated and the successful applications identified, they were reviewed by FNS-Cloud Coordinator for final sign off before the applicants are informed. Applicants were informed of the decision four weeks after close of submissions. Unsuccessful applicants were provided with feedback and invited to resubmit subsequently.

d. Financial information is sent to the home centre, which distributes the budget centrally

This was achieved by sending individual award emails to a nominated individual and providing a summary itemising the type of award (i.e., full, fixed value, travel only). Successful applicants were awarded 80% of estimated costs in advance to ensure ease of participation. However, 20% and any additional funding were awarded after completion of reporting and on presentation of receipts for the full costs.

e. Letters confirming awards are provided by the Scheme manager in soft copy, by email.

f. The deadline for receipts and a completed expense form, and the FNS-Cloud blog/webinar – from each recipient – is four weeks from the Monday following the final day of the training.

The aim of the blog/webinar was to encourage those receiving a grant to reflect on their learning, to describe how participation benefited them and might be employed by their organisation, and how it fits with FNS-Cloud wider goals; almost without exception, recipients find this part of the process most difficult regardless of location or seniority.

The assessment forms for evaluation of the submissions are provided in Appendix 1. These were kept deliberately simple to highlight the need for reflection.

Chapter 3: Evidencing reflection and learning

Reflection does not come naturally to some professionals particularly those from the scientific and analytical arenas. It is therefore considered critical to provide the applicants for these grants with some elearning materials that would allow them to write coherently in their applications when planning their learning and in their reflective accounts after the training/visits.

What you should aim to do when writing reflectively for assessment is to identify which aspects of a situation/critical incident or challenge are worthy of reflection. Your efforts to answer the questions raised, explore the motivations of yourself and others, and discuss the significance of unusual outcomes amount to an analysis (rather than just a description) of what happened. Such analysis is the key characteristic of reflective writing for assessment.

There is a great temptation to revert to descriptive writing which details every aspect of 'the story' but the review is not a story – it is an evaluative critical analysis of your learning to date. Only provide sufficient narrative to represent a context for the learning so its depth and impact can be assessed.

Considering an example here may be useful. In reflecting upon the learning needed to communicate well to large audiences you may describe the context as 'giving hour-long presentations to major internal scientific conferences with an audience of thought-leaders in your field'. The reader gets a clear picture of the capability required to do this effectively without needing to know how you were invited and who specifically was in the audience. The description is sufficient to differentiate the event from presenting to peers in departmental seminars. Having identified the context for the reader you can then go ahead to describe the learning you have achieved about giving such presentations.

An important point of note is that reflection is also not about orthodoxy. It is about transcendence, going beyond what is known and seeking new innovative solution to problems. But first you need to reflect on the notion of what has happened; what do you understand as the phenomena you have experienced.

The difference between reflection as a dynamic purposeful activity and reflexivity or other forms of contemplation is to emphasise, positive, responsible actions based on the learning experience context. It is based on a hermeneutic interpretation of experiences from a spectrum of points of view to gain an understanding which can improve future actions. Reflection in this sense does not just explore what was but considers what might have been, why it wasn't and how your personal actions can be brought to bear on similar situations to create a better outcome for all parties.

- Be evaluative and analytical rather than descriptive.
- Rather than just stating what capabilities you have developed, illustrate your claims with examples of how you have used them. For example, a statement such as, 'I have developed strong leadership skills' would need to be supported by a critical evaluation of what you determine those skills to be together with examples in which you deployed those skills.
- Remember that the focus is on the application of your specialist knowledge within your professional context (not on areas of specialist knowledge *per se*).
- Remember that you are seeking to link past and current learning to the projects you will go on to do later in your career.

- Adhere to standard ethical guidelines, for example, by avoiding reference to named individuals.
- Back up theoretical and reflective concepts you use with up-to-date references.

A model to assist in reflective writing.

To help in the process of reflective writing, Cox (2005) developed a model of structured reflection for writing may be beneficial. It has four central stages, the fourth of which links with the Kolb model:

- description of experience
- reflection on action
- influencing factors
- learning

In the first section, individuals might simply describe the phenomena or critical incident in their professional life upon which they intend to reflect.

At the second stage, these types of question could form the basis of a reflection:

What was I trying to achieve?

What reaction did I get?

How did I feel about the experience as it was happening?

How do I know how other people felt about it?

The third stage considers what internal and external influences were revealed in the incident; what did they say about the legitimacy of the aims and goals of the participants plus their knowledge?

The final stage raises questions concerning practice:

Could I have done things differently?

How do I feel about the experience now?

How did it make me more self-aware of my own role?

How might I change my behaviour to enact the consequences of your reflection?

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Appendix 1 Application form for practice-based learning grant

Information About You as Applicant

Your Family Name:

Your First Name:

Your Nationality:

Your 'Home' Organisation:

Present Organisation (if different from home organisation):

Name of Supervisor at your Home Organisation:

Is this training/collaboration part of the requirements of a Work Package? Yes/No (please delete as appropriate)

Does the training/collaboration you are wishing to undertake contribute to a specific deliverable of FNS-Cloud? Yes/No (delete as appropriate)

IF yes please specify which and how this contribution will be made

Please include a Personal Reflection (minimum 1 A4 Sheet) identifying how this visit/training has been selected to contribute to your personal/professional development.

Funds Requested

Estimated budgets are acceptable but FNS cloud reserves the right to refuse payment where there is a large discrepancy in costs

Signatures

Signature of Applicant

Date:

Signature of Head of Home Research Team or Manager

Date:

Appendix 2 Evaluator form for practice-based grant application for funds

Evaluator (name, acronym, partner number)	
Application number	
Feedback on application (recommendation to amend before resubmitting)	

Criteria	Score (1-5)	Comment
Eligibility of applicant	Please indicate yes or no	
Quality of Application Completeness of information Reason for applying Coherence of rationale for visit Potential impact on applicant in terms of professional development		
Relevance to FNS-cloud Added value to Project Contribution to deliverables		
Overall evaluation	Please indicate accept or reject	